

Evaluation of Personal Hygiene among Female Students Age Group (18-22) Years

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Abstract:- Personal hygiene is mandatory for female students to prevent many diseases. Personal hygiene helps females to stay healthy. Poor personal hygiene is more prone to Vulnerable infection. Good hygienic practices teach from their early life, and it helps to create self- awareness. This study was conducted to assess the practice of personal hygiene among female students age group (18 - 22) years at Sree Ramakrishna Medical College of Naturopathy and Yogic Sciences and Hospital, Kulasekharam, Tamil Nadu, India. The study units were female students age group (18 - 22) years. The study is designed as a questionnaire and is distributed to Female Students. Verbal consent was taken from the female students by explaining the purpose of the study. The total number of study respondents was 30. The questionnaire contains 30 questions. The Parameters of the questionnaire included sociodemographic information and hygienic practices. The hygienic practices included cloth hygiene, skin hygiene, oral hygiene, hair hygiene, hand hygiene, urogenital hygiene, ear hygiene, bowel hygiene, and mental hygiene. From this study the practice of personal hygiene about wearing washed clothes and regular head bath are satisfactory but scalp hygiene, water intake and sleep are very poor. Therefore, female students need more awareness about scalp hygiene, water intake, and sleep.

Keywords:- Hygiene, Personal hygiene, Menstrual hygiene, Genital hygiene, Sanitation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The word hygiene is derived from the Greek word “Hygeia,” the goddess of health. Her disciples were called hygienists, who practiced hygiene for health. Hygiene is defined, as the science of health and embraces all factors contributing to healthful living. Hygiene was given an important place in ancient Indian medicine. The “Laws of Manu” were a code of personal hygiene. According to health education, hygiene has two aspects, Personal and Environmental hygiene. Environmental hygiene includes domestic and community hygiene. Personal hygiene aims to promote standards of personal cleanliness within the setting of the condition where people live. Personal hygiene includes bathing, clothing, washing hands and toilet, care of

nails, feet, and teeth, spitting, coughing, sneezing, personal appearance inculcation of clean habits in the young. Training in personal hygiene should begin at a very early age and must be carried through school age. Personal hygiene is very mandatory for female students to prevent many diseases. Personal hygiene helps females to stay healthy. Poor personal hygiene is more prone to Vulnerable infection. Good hygienic practices teach from their early life, and it helps to create self-awareness.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The study was a descriptive type of cross-sectional study conducted in July 2022 to assess basic components of personal hygiene. The study units were female students age group (18 - 22) years at Sree Ramakrishna Medical College of Naturopathy and Yogic Sciences and Hospital, Kulasekharam,(T.N.) India. The study is designed as a questionnaire and is distributed to female students. Verbal consent was taken from the female students by explaining the purpose of the study. The total number of study respondents n=30. The questionnaire contains 30 questions. The parameters of the questionnaire included sociodemographic information and hygienic practices. The hygienic practices included cloth hygiene, skin hygiene, oral hygiene, hair hygiene, hand hygiene, urogenital hygiene, ear hygiene, bowel hygiene, and mental hygiene. Those females who did not cooperate and were non-willing to participate were excluded from the study.

III. RESULT

The sociodemographic character showed that the respondents belonged between (18 - 22) years of age. The total number of female students is n=30. Table 1.1 shows, regular early morning wake up 26(86.66%), while 4(13.33%) do not have the practice of early morning wake up. Brushing habit two times per day 9(30%), and 21(70%) do not have this habit. Defecation per day 27(90%), and 3(10%) not having the habit of this matter. Everyone takes head bath per day 30(100%), has tartar teeth 3(10%) and 27(90%) do not have tartar teeth. Have tooth decay 7(23.33%), and 23(76.66%) do not have tooth decay. Have gingivitis 1(3.33%), and 29(96.66%) not having gingivitis. Regular tongue cleaning 23(76.66%), and 7(23.33%) do not

clean their tongue regularly. Dandruff on scalp 17(56.66%), and 13(43.33%) do not have dandruff on the scalp. Have hair fall 29(96.66%) and 1(3.33%) do not have hair fall. Have lice on the scalp 14(46.66%)and 16(53.33%) do not

have lice on the scalp. Regular oil application on scalp 20(66.66%) and 10(33.33%) do not have the habit of regular oil application on the scalp.

SS.No	CONTENTS	YES	PPERCENTAGE (%)	NO	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Regular Early Morning Wake-up	26	86.66	4	13.33
2	Brushing Habit two times per day	9	30.00	21	70.00
3	Defecation Per Day	27	90.00	3	10.00
4	Head Bath Per Day	30	100.00	-	-
5	Do You Have Tartar Teeth	3	10.00	27	90.00
6	Do You Have Tooth Decay	7	23.33	23	76.66
7	Do You Have gingivitis	1	3.33	29	96.66
8	Do You Clean your Tongue Regularly	23	76.66	7	23.33
9	Dandruff on your Scalp	17	56.66	13	43.33
10	Do you have hair fall	29	96.66	1	3.33
11	Do you have Lice on your Scalp	14	46.66	16	53.33
12	Oil application on Scalp Regularly	20	66.66	10	33.33
13	Eye Boogers after Wake up	18	60.00	12	40.00
14	Acne on your Face	17	56.66	13	43.33
15	Wash your Face Frequently	27	90.00	3	10.00
16	Habit of ear cleaning Regularly	19	63.33	11	36.66
17	Do you have ear discharges	2	6.66	28	93.33
18	Habit of hand Washing Regularly	29	96.66	1	3.33
19	Have the habit of nails trim	24	80.00	6	20.00
20	Frequency of Micturate 5-6 times per day	16	53.33	14	46.66
21	Do you intake 3-4 liters of water per day	7	23.33	23	76.66
22	Do you wear washed clothes regularly	30	100.00	-	-
23	Do you prefer cotton inner wear	22	73.33	8	26.66
24	Do you change your inner wear two times per day	11	36.66	19	63.33
25	Do you change sanitary napkins Frequently	30	100.00	-	-
26	Do you have Urinary Tract Infection	6	20.00	24	80.00
27	Do you have the symptoms of white discharge	17	56.66	13	43.33
28	Do you have the symptoms of Fungal Infection	3	10.00	27	90.00
29	Are you sleep 8 hours per day	6	20.00	24	80.00
30	Do you have sound sleep	9	30.00	21	70.00

Table 1: shows the percentage of personal hygiene in female students of age group (18 - 22) years.

Fig. 1: shows the percentage of YES response

Fig. 2: shows the percentage of response No

Eye boogers after waking up 18(60%) and 12(40%) do not have eye boogers after waking up. Acne on face 17(56.66%) and 13(43.33%) do not have acne on face. Face washing frequently 27(90%) and 3(10%) are not washing face frequently. The regular habit of ear cleaning 19(63.33%) and 11(36.66%) do not have the habit of regular ear cleaning. Have ear discharges 2(6.66%) and 28(93.33%) do not have ear discharges. The regular habit of hand washing 29(96.66%) and 1(3.33%) do not have a regular habit of hand washing. Have the habit of having their nails trimmed 24(80%) and 6(20%) do not have the habit of nails trimmed. Frequency of micturition 5-6 times per day for 16(53.33%) and 14(46.66%) do not have the frequency of micturition 5-6 times per day. Intake of 3-4 liters of water per day 7(23.33%) and 23(76.66%) do not drink 3-4 liters of water per day. Everyone wears washed clothes 30(100%). Prefer cotton innerwear 22(73.33%) and 8(26.66%) do not prefer cotton innerwear. Changing the inner wear two times per day 11(36.66%) and 19(63.33%) do not change the inner wear two times per day. Everyone changes the sanitary napkins frequently 30(100%). Have urinary tract infections 6(20%) and 24(80%) do not have urinary tract infection. Have the symptoms of white discharge 17(56.66%) and 13(43.33%) do not have the symptoms of white discharge. Have the symptoms of fungal infection 3(10%) and 27(90%) do not have the symptoms of fungal infection. Sleep 8 hours per day 6(20%) and 24(80%) do not sleep 8 hours per day. Have sound sleep 9(30%) and 21(70%) do not have sound sleep.

IV. DISCUSSION

Regular early morning wake up 26(86.66%), The majority of female students wake up in the early morning, Brushing habit two times per day 9(30%), only fewer students having this habit. Defecation per day 27(90%), Everyone is taking head bath everyday 30(100%), Have tartar teeth 3(10%), Have tooth decay 7(23.33%) fewer female students have tartar and tooth decay. Have gingivitis 1(3.33%), Regular tongue cleaning 23(76.66%) majority of students clean the tongue, Dandruff on scalp 17(56.66%), Have hair fall 29(96.66%), Have lice on the scalp

14(46.66%), Regular oil application on scalp 20(66.66%), most of the female students have dandruff on scalp and hair fall. Eye boogers after waking up 18(60%). Acne on face 17(56.66%). Face washing frequently 27(90%).The regular habit of ear cleaning 19(63.33%). Have ear discharges 2(6.66%). The regular habit of handwashing is 29(96.66%), trimming nails 24(80%), and most of the female students have the habit of trimming nails. Frequency of micturition 5-6 times per day 16(53.33%), and 23(76.66%) are not taking 3-4 liters of water per day, so they need awareness about water intake. Everyone wears washed clothes regularly 30(100%). Prefer cotton innerwear 22(73.33%), and 19(63.33%) do not change their innerwear two times per day. Everyone is changing sanitary napkins frequently 30(100%). Have urinary tract infection 6(20%). Have the symptoms of white discharge 17(56.66%), and most of the female students have white discharge. Have the symptoms of fungal infection 3(10%), and 24(80%) do not sleep 8 hours per day. 21(70%) do not have sound sleep. The Majority of female students are not having the awareness of the importance of sleep.

V. CONCLUSION

From this study's result and discussion, it is concluded that the practice of personal hygiene by wearing washed clothes and regular head baths is satisfactory but scalp hygiene, water intake, and sleep are very poor. Female students were more conscious about genital hygiene. Therefore, they need more awareness about scalp hygiene, water intake, and sleep.

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